

METHODOLOGICAL PRINCIPLES SPECIFIC TO SOCIO-CULTURAL DEVELOPMENT

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Wide application of the achievements of scientific and technical development in the social life of the 20th century brought about radical changes in the content and essence of reproductive and innovative types of activity. Increasing attention to the human factor, the desire to fully satisfy his needs has made the creation of innovations and their introduction a vital necessity, and has led to the emergence of special institutional structures that serve to conduct innovative activities. The creation of a system of legal, economic, and social institutions for the management of science, material and spiritual stimulation, and the direct implementation of new ideas and solutions has had a positive effect on the formation of a holistic innovative space in society. .

It is natural that the innovative activity carried out within the framework of special institutional structures equipped on a scientific and technical basis will have a good effect, especially for the creation and justification of an innovative idea and a conceptual basis, a separate, integrated activity is extremely important. Based on practical experiences, it can be said that in order to achieve efficiency in innovative activities, the substantiation of these ideas and the direct connection with practice in finding a solution is considered a suitable factor. Such efforts are the reason for the growing tendency to ensure organic connection between science and production. The introduction of information technology into all aspects of creative activity creates favorable conditions for the interdependence of reproductive and innovative activities, increases the efficiency of finding a clear technological solution of a theoretical idea as an expression of a new idea and implementing it directly into practice.

It is self-evident that drawing conclusions from the lessons of history, managing social life based on democratic, humanitarian criteria is desirable in all respects. The formation of a new worldview called for finding ways to rationally organize social and cultural activities. As a product of such a new way of thinking, full realization of human rights and freedoms, protection of his interests was evaluated as a priority. In order to consistently implement this, first of all, it was necessary to determine the issue of ensuring social development and management in accordance with the spirit of the times.

The desire to interpret society and human philosophy from the point of view of a new worldview required specific methodological principles of socio-

cultural development. The idea of a gradual process of social development forms the basis of such a worldview. Consequently, it helps to interpret the laws of circular movement of social life.

Gradual development is based on the law of development of both natural and social existence. After all, the internal balance of the natural being is preserved only when social events take place in harmony, and there is an opportunity to change it and subjugate it to human interests. But gradual development is a long process. Man tries to speed up this process by using the capabilities of his intelligence. After all, in this way, the opportunities to meet the growing needs of a person can be expanded.

It is a legitimate process to use different methods in managing social processes with the help of socio-cultural potential. For example, in the recent past, progress was made by revolutionary leaps, which led to serious problems unprecedented in human history.

In conclusion, the development strategy of the new development path of our country envisages the assimilation of the achievements of modern civilization by modernizing all spheres of social life in the spirit of nationalism according to the criteria of universal development. Because the destructive effect of the achievements of modern social development on national-cultural traditions and values is observed, and its consequences leave their traces in the consciousness of young people. The consumer society enables the transition to the innovative stage with the rise of moral and moral culture of young people.

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